

Tackling Trash: My Perspective on Waste Management in India

Author: Harendra Kumar, Ph.D.

Email: harendrakumarphd@gmail.com

Abstract

This note reflects waste management crisis in India, emphasizing that the core issue lies not in technology or civic sense, but in the absence of an effective, enforced system. Drawing on personal experience and examples, it argues for prioritizing waste infrastructure to foster civic responsibility and drive meaningful waste management change.

Discussion

In India, waste management has never truly been a national priority. However, that is beginning to change. Plastic and textile waste continue to be dumped in landfills, and often end up littering the streets and waterways¹. But is this merely an issue of civic sense or a lack of technological advancement? In my opinion, it is neither.

The real issue lies in the absence of a well-established system—or in cases where systems do exist, their failure is often due to a lack of vision and enforcement, starting from the highest levels of government down to local towns and villages.

Having lived in Japan, I personally follow strict waste management rules. But when I return to India, I find myself disposing of waste just like most others around me. This shows that civic sense develops only after a proper waste management system is in place.

Consider another example: when scientists or professors work at institutions surrounded by waste-filled streets and waterways—some of them even researching waste management—it becomes clear that technical expertise alone cannot resolve the problem. The truth is, without a functioning ground-level system, no amount of laboratory research or technological advancement will bring about real change.

As a nation, we must prioritize the creation and implementation of effective waste management systems. By "system," I mean an organized, reliable chain of waste collection and transportation to recycling facilities. When people know that a waste collector will come to door next day, they will likely wait and even say "thank you" for the service.

Conclusions

In conclusion, the core issue is that waste management has not been treated as a national priority—when it absolutely should be. For a healthy and truly developing nation, this must change.

What are your thoughts?

References

1 Department of Economic and Social Affairs, Sustainable Development, United Nations, <https://sdgs.un.org/>